

RESPONSIVENESS AND CUSTOMER PATRONAGE OF MICROFINANCE BANKS IN AKWA IBOM STATE, NIGERIA

¹Aniekan Eyo Awah, ²Aniefiok Okon Akpan and ³Diala Ogadinma Emmanuel

^{1,2}Department of Marketing, Akwa Ibom State University, Obio Akpa Campus

³Department of Marketing, University of Uyo, Akwa Ibom State.

E-mail anieyo12@gmail.com. *E-mail* ogadid@yahoo.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10814441>

Abstract: The main objective of this study was to examine the influence of responsiveness on Customer patronage of Microfinance banks in Akwa Ibom State. To achieve this objective, the main source of data was through primary sources with the use of a questionnaire. The researcher adopted the survey research design approach and data were collected from 323 respondents drawn from the banks customers' base. A total number of 295 copies of the questionnaire were retrieved in useable form representing 91.3 percent, data was analyzed using the Simple Regression Model (SRM). Data generated from the study were processed using descriptive and inferential statistics and hypothesis tested at 0.05 level of significance. Findings revealed that responsiveness had significant influence on customer patronage of Microfinance banks in Akwa Ibom State. Thus, the study recommends that Microfinance banks employees should Show willingness to help their customers as well as providing prompt service to aid build customers trust, exceed their expectations and enhance their patronage.

Keywords: Customer patronage, Macro Finance, Banks, Responsiveness, Services and Efficiency

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the Study

There is need for services to be adapted to the dynamic changes in our business environment. Today, with the new design of the naira, the new withdrawal limit set and the scarcity of the naira notes in circulation. Banks have experience huge influx of their existing and potential customers all requiring good, quick, urgent and quality service delivery.

Internationally, the banking industry is now very competitive which makes the deposit money banks competing for Microfinance banks customers. The emergence of new deposit money banks and the emergence of new Microfinance banks have made their customers to be more sophisticated now requesting for quality service delivery (Osim, Muyanja and T. bainyana, 2020). Due to this, banking firms are taking advantage of technology to differentiate their service delivery as the industry has become more competitive (Osim et.al. 2020). Automated teller machine, online/internet banking, telephone banking, mobile banking and SMS banking are some of the self-service technologies being used to meet customers banking needs. The convenience of use, security of transactions, ease of use, quality of information delivery and reliability of technology are all part of these self-service technologies (Osim. et.al. 2020; Akpan, 2007).

Technology with excellent service quality can aid the bank customers to make online purchase using the banks online banking platforms. Accordingly, Chattopadhyay (2019) is of the view that the success of Microfinance Banks (MFB) depends mainly on customer satisfaction. In successful business organization, customers are their priority before the profits. Hence, MFB should set their monetary value in equivalent with their service quality in order to attract and maintain long term relationship with their customers. This will lead to increase in the number of both their existing and potential customers as well as translate into good customer patronage (Chattopadhyay, 2019). Okeke (2020) viewed customer patronage as the critical component for increase in the banks profit as well as aid in the maintenance of the banks' position.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Repeatedly, customers have experienced the unreliability of technology services when using ATMs. Many have reported visiting these machines only to find them either out of service or without sufficient cash to carry out their transactions. On the other hand, clients who try to access their money through the mobile phone banking channel have reported failure due to process complexity, i.e. they can either acquire it through the mobile application (app) compatible only with android phones or the unstructured supplementary service data (USSD) of which the session time out is very short rendering it unfavorable for some customers. (Akpan and Abdul, 2009; Osinde, Mayanja and Tibaingana, 2020).

Unfortunately, there have been several studies (see for example, Akpan,2007, Acha, 2012; Wardhana and Satriyanto, 2020; Alshammari, Mahmond and Daud, 2021; Njagi and Njoku, 2021) on the activities of Microfinance Banks but little effort have been done in the area service quality and customer patronage of Microfinance Banks in developing economies like Nigeria. More so, many studies on financial institutions have been focusing on deposit money banks with very little effort on Microfinance Banks particularly in Nigeria (Cai, Park and Wang, 2016). This obvious knowledge gap was the main impetus for conducting this study.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study was to examine the influence of responsiveness on customer patronage of selected Microfinance Banks in Akwa Ibom State.

1.4 Research Questions

This study attempted to provide answers to the following question.

- ❖ What is the influence of responsiveness on customer patronage of Microfinance Banks in Akwa Ibom state

1.5 Hypothesis

- The following null hypothesis were postulated to guide the study:
- Responsiveness does not significantly influence customer patronage of Microfinance Banks in Akwa Ibom State.

1.6 Significance of the Study

This study will provide insights into how effective customer service and responsiveness influence customers decisions to engage with microfinance institutions, potentially contributing to financial stability and community development.

1.7 Scope of the Study

The scope of the study covered the following three central aspects:

Content Scope: The content scope of this study covers the service quality variable used by Microfinance Banks in Akwa Ibom State such as responsiveness and customer patronage. It also covers the concepts on responsiveness and customer patronage. This study was domiciled in service marketing.

Geographical Scope: The geographical scope of the study was in Akwa Ibom State located at the South South region of Nigeria.

Unit of Analysis: The unit of analysis of this study involved customers of the selected Microfinance Banks in Akwa Ibom State, namely: Uniuyo microfinance bank, Palmcoast microfinance bank, Active point microfinance bank, Eduiek microfinance bank, Ikpe-Annang microfinance banks, Ini microfinance bank, Madelyn microfinance bank, Nsehe microfinance bank and Akcofed microfinance bank.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Conceptual Framework

2.1.1 Concept of Service Quality

The relative superiority of the banks and its service is presented in service quality hence, service quality is important for the survival of all servicing companies, (Chattopadhyay, 2019).

Service quality is seen as a form of attitude, maintaining service quality at certain levels and improving service quality is a lifetime effort for banks who want life time prosperity for their customers, (Chattopadhyay, 2019). It is possible to retain the right customers with service quality. Therefore, it is a priority to retain profitable customers and form customer equity. Service quality can be used by banks to gain competitive advantage, it can also be used as a tool to differentiate a bank from its competitors. Good service can attract potential customers and keep existing customers, (Daramawam, Mardikaningsih & Hadi, 2017).

Zebra and Zaveri (2020) in their study focused on the effect of service quality on customer loyalty; a study of hotels in Ethiopia. Their results revealed that tangibility had a positive and statistically significant association with hotel customers' loyalty, reliability had a positive and statistically significant relationship with hotel customers' loyalty.

Darmawan *et al.*, (2017) pointed out in their study that service quality had a significant positive effect on customer satisfaction, corporate image and customer loyalty in the banking sector in Indonesia. In their view, service quality can create and enhance customer patronage and corporate image in the banking industry.

Okeke (2020) in his study focused on the effect of food quality, service quality, physical environment and price on the patronage of local restaurants in Awka, Anambra State. Their result revealed that all the independent variables apart from price used in the study were significant determinants of customer patronage in local food restaurant in Awka. Their study also revealed that food quality was the most statistically determinant of customer patronage of local restaurant followed by service quality and physical environment.

Molae, Ansari and Teimuori (2013) pointed out in their study on analyzing the impact of service quality dimensions on customer satisfaction and loyalty in the banking industry of Iran. Their study showed that responsiveness, tangibility, reliability and compliance had a direct and significant effect on customer satisfaction. Leninkumar (2016) in his study focused on the effect of service quality on customer loyalty. The findings of their study revealed that the three dimensions of service quality namely reliability, tangibility and empathy had significant positive effect on customer loyalty. Kuo, Tsai, Iuan-yuan and Chang (2017) posits in

their study on the relationship among service quality, customer satisfaction and customer loyalty, a case study on mobile shopping Apps. The findings of their study showed that privacy/ security, reliability and tangibility were the main factors in the measurement of mobile shopping application. Abioro and Odunlami (2021) postulated in their study on the Implication of product branding on customer's patronage in the Nigerian consumer goods industry. They found out that brand perception had a significant effect on customer patronage, their study also revealed that service quality significantly affect customer patronage. Awaji-Ima and Carl (2022) in their study focused on the service quality delivery and customer patronage of deposit money banks in Port Harcourt. Their study revealed a significant relationship between service quality delivery and customer patronage. Rahman, Hossain, Zaman and Mannan (2020) pointed out in their study on E- Service quality and trust on customers' patronage intention. The result of their findings revealed that customers' trust plays a significant role in mediating the relationship between e-service quality and customers' patronage intentions. Abdul-Qadir, Abubakar and Utomi (2021) pointed out in their study on the impact of service quality on customer retention of listed food and beverage companies in Kaduna State. The findings of their study revealed a positive and significant effect of service quality on customer retention. Obananya (2020) in their study focused on service quality and customers' loyalty in Nigerian commercial banking industry. Their study findings revealed that tangibility, reliability, responsiveness and assurance had significant influence on customer loyalty in the banking industry. Khan and Fasih (2014) in their study focused on the impact of service quality on customer satisfaction and customer loyalty. Their study showed that all the dimensions of service quality had a significant and positive relationship with customer satisfaction and customer loyalty. Juudeh and Dandis (2018) pointed out in their study on the influence of service quality (internet service quality) on customer loyalty through the mediating effect of customer satisfaction. The findings of their study showed that internet service quality had a positive influence on customer satisfaction as well as influence the level of customer loyalty. Subiyantoro (2021) in his study focused on the effect of service quality, convenience, price and product quality on customer satisfaction and customer loyalty. The study findings showed that the ease and the quality of the product had a significant effect on customer loyalty. Also, service quality, convenience, price and product quality all had significant effect on Customer loyalty. Customer satisfaction as well had a significant effect on customer loyalty. Akbar, Som, Wadood and Alzaidiyeen (2010) investigated the relationship between hotel service quality failure, customer perceived value, revitalization of the service quality, customer satisfaction and loyalty in the hotel industry. The findings of this study revealed that hotel revitalization of service quality had positive effects on customer loyalty, perceived value and customer satisfaction were the two significant variables that mediated the relationships between the hotel service quality and customer loyalty. The study also revealed that the hotel service quality had no significant and direct effect rather an indirect positive effect on customer satisfaction.

2.1.2 SERVICE QUALITY GAP

Kotler and Armstrong (2020) propose the existence of five gaps that contribute to unsuccessful service delivery, detailed as follows: Gap between consumer expectation and management perception:

Management may not always accurately perceive customer desires. For instance, the bank might assume that customers prioritize the availability of loans, while customers may actually be more concerned with the responsiveness of the staff. Gap between management perception and service quality specification:

Although management might correctly perceive customer needs, they may fail to establish performance standards. Gap between service quality specification and service delivery:

This gap can arise when personnel are inadequately trained, incapable, or unwilling to meet the established standards. Conflicting standards, such as balancing time spent listening to customers and providing fast service, can also contribute to this gap.

Gap between service delivery and external communications:

Customer expectations are influenced by statements made by company representatives and advertisements. If the bank's promotional materials depict an elegant banking hall, but customers arrive to find it cheap and unimpressive, external communications have distorted customer expectations. Gap between perceived service and expected service: This gap occurs when customers misperceive the quality of the service in comparison to their expectations.

2.1.3 Customer Patronage

A bank that gets a good number of customers who patronize its service is considered successful. Banks want to have satisfied customers who return to make more transactions, (Anetoh, 2016). Customer satisfaction is a factor used to cheer customers to use the service again although a satisfied customer may not always return for a repeat purchase (Nnamdi, 2020). Quality services should be rendered by banks in order to build goodwill and attract consistent customer patronage (Anetoh, 2016).

Accordingly, Smith (2012) shows 5 hints on how to ensure persistent customer patronage. These include building a good personal relationship with your customers, not being rude to customers, maintaining integrity, rewarding customer's patronage and by adding value to the society. With these tips, quality service will be improved for enhanced customer patronage and satisfaction.

Rahman, Hossain, Zaman and Mannan (2020) found out that customer's trust plays a significant role in mediating the relationship between e-service quality and customer's patronage intentions. The adoption of advanced technology proved to be a significant moderator in explaining trust and customer's patronage intention in online retail banking setting.

Anetoh (2016) in a study, on the dimensions of service quality and customer patronage of grocery services in Nigeria, revealed a significant relationship between service quality dimensions and customer patronage of grocery services in Nigeria. He also found out that SERVPERF model was a useful tool in measuring service quality and customer patronage of Nigerian grocery services.

2.1.4 Responsiveness and Customer Patronage

Responsiveness refers to the willingness of service providers to assist customers and provide prompt services. Osinde, Mayanja and Tibaingana (2020) postulated in their study on technology service quality and customer satisfaction in the Uganda's banking sector. The study of their study revealed that technology service quality such as responsiveness and security had no significant impact on customer satisfaction. Mwirigi (2019) in his study investigated the mediating effect of service quality on the relationship between customer relationship management (CRM) and the satisfaction of commercial bank account holders in Nairobi city county, Kenya. The findings of the study revealed that service quality dimensions has a statistically significant mediating effect on the relationship between CRM and the satisfaction of commercial account bank holders. Setiawan, Rini and Silalahi (2022) in their study on the effect of electronic service quality and perceived value on customer loyalty

through customer satisfaction as a mediating variable for participation in Bpjamsostek Medan city branch. The result of this study revealed that perceived value affect customer loyalty either directly or indirectly through customer satisfaction as a moderating variable while e- service quality variables did not influence customer loyalty either directly or indirectly through customer satisfaction as moderating variables.

2.2 Theoretical Framework

In this section one major theories were considered relevant for this study; they include;

2.2.1 Service Performance (SERVPERF) Model Propounded by Cronin, J. and Taylor, S. (1992)

The SERVPERF model measures quality as an attitude rather than satisfaction. Thus, the model uses the idea of perceived service quality which leads to satisfaction. The model then corrects satisfaction with further purchase intentions. The SERVPERF model is a modification of SERVQUAL and uses the same dimensions of SERVQUAL to assess service quality which include the following; tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance and empathy and they proposed a 22 performance items related.

This model is used in the banking industry to measure customer service performance. Banks uses this model to evaluate how quickly their customers are assisted, how transactions are accurately processed, and how the banks stuffs are helpful when customers have questions.

2.3 Review of Empirical Studies

This section is concerned with the review of the studies which were considered to be relevant, accordingly 10 studies were reviewed.

2.3.1 Awaji – Ima and Carl (2022): Service quality delivery and customer patronage of deposit money banks in Port Harcourt. They attempted to ascertain the relationship between service quality delivery and customer patronage of deposit money banks in Port Harcourt. They adopted inferential and descriptive statistics for data analysis. The findings of the study revealed a significant relationship between service quality delivery and customer patronage of deposit money banks in Port Harcourt. The study concluded that the Panacea for customer patronage is effective service delivery. They recommended that deposit money banks especially those in Rivers State should be responsive in terms of their service delivery as it would enhance customer patronage. Critics: The research successfully established the significant relationship between service quality delivery and customer patronage of deposit money banks in Port Harcourt, providing valuable managerial guidance for enhancing customer patronage through effective service delivery.

2.3.2 Rahman, *et al.*, (2020):E–Service quality and trust on customer’s patronage intention, Moderation effect of adoption of advanced technologies. They attempted to investigate the role of trust as well as the relationship between e–service quality and customers’ patronage intention in the online retail banking. They adopted the inferential and descriptive statistics for data analysis. The result of their findings showed that customer’s trust plays a significant role in mediating the relationship between e-service quality and customers’ patronage intentions. They concluded that the adoption of advanced technologies has proved to be a significant moderator which explains trust and customers’ patronage intention in online and retail banking setting. They recommended that policy makers should implement and use marketing strategies by designing high-quality websites, they should target relevant market segments as well as facilitating the use of electronic commerce. Critics: This study was carried out in the context of Bangladesh and may not be applicable to the Nigerian business environment particularly in Uyo Metropolis, Akwa Ibom State also the study effectively investigated

the role of trust and the relationship between e-service quality and customer patronage intention in online retail banking, providing relevant recommendations for policy makers to implement marketing strategies.

2.3.3 Abdul-Qadir *et al.*, (2021): Impact of service quality on customer retention of listed food and beverages companies in Kaduna State. The study attempted to investigate the effect of service quality on customer retention of listed food and beverages companies in Kaduna State. They adopted inferential and descriptive statistics for data analysis. The findings of this study revealed a positive and significant effect of service quality on customer intention. The study concluded that service quality has significant influence on customer retention of listed food and beverage Company. The study recommended that management of the firm should give all employers equal opportunity irrespective of service quality in order to aid in enhancing effective organizational performance and customer retention. Critics: This study was carried out in Kaduna State hence the findings of this study may not be applicable in other business environments and also the study effectively explored the impact of service quality on customer retention of listed food and beverages companies in Kaduna State and offered valuable recommendations for enhancing customer retention.

2.3.4 Obananya (2020): Service quality and customers' loyalty in Nigerian Commercial banking industry. Obananya attempted to study the effect of tangibility, reliability, responsiveness and assurance on customer loyalty. The study adopted the simple percentage analysis and multiple regression analysis for data analysis. The findings of the study showed that tangibility, reliability, responsiveness and assurance had significant influence on customer loyalty in the banking industry. The study concluded that there was a link between service quality and the level of customer loyalty. The study recommended that managers of financial institutions should adopt a win-win service quality strategy that can deliver value and satisfaction to their customers making them loyal to their organizations. Critics: The study failed to use the single regression analysis to find out the individual effect of each dimension of the service quality on customer loyalty also the research successfully studied the effect of service quality dimensions on customer loyalty in the Nigerian commercial banking industry, but it missed the opportunity to analyze the individual effects of each dimension, limiting its practical application.

2.3.5 Khan and Fasih (2014): Impact of service quality on customer satisfaction and customer loyalty, evidence from banking sector. Khan and Fasih attempted to find out the banking customers level of satisfaction considering different service quality provided by the banks and their loyalty with regard to those banks. They adopted the inferential and descriptive statistics for data analysis. The findings of the study revealed that all the dimensions of service quality had a significant and positive relationship with customer satisfaction and customer loyalty. The study recommended that managers of financial institutions should innovate their service to meet the needs and demands of their customers. Critics: This study was carried out in 2014, it may not be applicable in today's dynamic business environment due to changes in our business environment also the study effectively demonstrated the significant relationship between service quality, customer satisfaction, and loyalty in the banking sector, although its relevance might be limited due to changes in the business environment since its publication in 2014.

2.3.6 Juudeh and Dandis (2018): Service quality, customer satisfaction and loyalty in an internet service provider. They attempted to investigate the influence of service quality (Internet service quality) on customer loyalty through the mediating effect of customer satisfaction. They adopted inferential and description statistics

for data analysis. The findings of this study showed that internet service quality had a positive influence on customer satisfaction as well as influence the level of customer loyalty. They concluded that an excellently well-built service quality may lead to customer satisfaction which can translate into a better level of customer loyalty. They recommended that the managers of the internet service providers should enhance the level of service quality awareness as this was the best approach to customer satisfaction. Employees who are aware of this tend to pay extra attention to the service quality concept which can translate to a better customer loyalty. Critics: The study was conducted in a developed economy and may not be applicable to most developing economics like Nigeria and also the research successfully investigated the influence of internet service quality on customer loyalty mediated by customer satisfaction, yet its applicability to developing economies like Nigeria remains uncertain.

2.3.7 Subiyantoro (2021): The effect of service quality, convenience, price, product quality on satisfaction and customer loyalty of funding PT Bank Mandiri in Surabaya. The study attempted to investigate the effect of service quality, convenience, price and product quality on customer satisfaction and customer loyalty. They adopted the partial least square for data analysis. The findings of this study revealed that the ease and quality of the product has a significant effect on customer satisfaction. Also, service quality, convenience, price and product quality all had a significant effect on customer loyalty. Customer satisfaction as well had a significant effect on customer loyalty. Critics: The study had no recommendation to guide business managers in making strategic business decision. Hence, no managerial implications also the study successfully investigated the impact of service quality, commerce, price, and product quality on customer satisfaction and loyalty; however, its lack of managerial implications limits its practical value for guiding business decisions.

2.3.8 Alafashat and Alola (2018): Investigating the nexus of service quality and customer loyalty in banking industry via the mediating role of customer satisfaction. Alafashat and Alola attempted to examine the relationship between service quality, customer satisfaction and customer loyalty in the Jordanian commercial bank. Their study also examined customer satisfaction as a partial mediator of the impact of service quality on customer loyalty. They adopted inferential and descriptive statistics. The result of their findings revealed that there is a significant positive relationship between all the five dimensions of service quality with customer satisfaction. It also revealed that there is a significant effect of all the dimensions of service quality apart from reliability dimension on customer loyalty. Their findings further revealed that customer satisfaction partially mediates between the five dimensions of service quality and customer loyalty. They recommended that the bank management should take action in improving the bank equipment and design in order to create a proper atmosphere for customers. They should also provide periodical training programs for their employees to improve their skills and know-how to be able to solve customer problems and meet customer satisfaction. Critics: The study may not be applicable in the Nigerian business environment also this study effectively explored the relationship between service quality, customer satisfaction, and loyalty in the Jordanian commercial bank, and its recommendation to improve bank equipment and employee training adds practical value for enhancing customer experience.

2.3.9 Akbar, *et al.*, (2010): Revitalization of service quality to gain customer satisfaction and loyalty. Their study attempted to investigate the relationship between hotel service quality failure, customer perceived value, revitalization of service quality, customer satisfaction and loyalty in the hotel industry. Inferential and

descriptive statistics was adopted in this study for data analysis. The findings of this study showed that hotel revitalization of service quality had positive effects on Customer Loyalty, perceived value and customer satisfaction were the two significant variables that mediated the relationships between the hotel service quality and customer loyalty. The study also revealed that the hotel service quality had no significant and direct effect rather an indirect positive effect on customer satisfaction. Critics: The study had no recommendations as a guide to business managers in making informed strategic decision also while this study provided insights into the relationship between hotel service quality failure, perceived value, and customer satisfaction, its lack of direct effects for hotel service quality on customer satisfaction and the absence of recommendations hinder its application for business decisions.

2.3.10 Ismail and Yunam (2016): Service quality as a predictor of Customer Satisfaction and Customer Loyalty. Ismail and Yunam attempted to investigate the correlation between service quality and customer loyalty and the correlation between service quality and customer loyalty. They adopted the inferential and descriptive statistics for data analysis, the findings of their study revealed that service quality dimensions such as tangibility, reliability, responsiveness, assurance and empathy significantly correlates with the customer satisfaction and customer loyalty. They concluded that the ability of service providers to appropriately implement the quality dimensions in providing medical service has enhance customer loyalty and satisfaction in the organization. They recommended that the findings of their study should be used as important guidelines by management to improve the implementation of service quality in Malaysian Army Health Centers. Critics: This study was carried out in 2016 and may not be relevant in today's dynamic business environment hence the need for recent research also the study effectively demonstrated the significant correlation between service quality dimensions and customer satisfaction and loyalty in the Malaysian Army Health Centers and offered valuable recommendations for managerial improvements; however, its relevance in the current business environment might be limited.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Design of the Study

The study design adopted by the researcher in this study was the Survey Research Design. Data on the three independent variables and the dependent variable were collected from different microfinance banks in Akwa Ibom State. The survey research design used assisted the researcher in reaching out to a good number of customers of Microfinance Banks in Akwa Ibom State.

3.2 Population of the Study

The target population for the study comprised all customers of Microfinance Banks in Akwa Ibom State. Hence, the Population of the study was infinite,

3.3 Sampling and the Sample Size determination

Since the population size for the study was infinite, sample size for this study was determined using the Topman Formula at 5% level of tolerable error.

The formula is given as

$$n = \frac{Z^2 \cdot pq}{e^2}$$

Where n = required sample size

z = the value of z-score associated with the degree of confidence is 95% confidence level being 1.96 from the Z-score table.

p = 0.7 decimal (positive)

q = 0.3 decimal (negative)

e = acceptable tolerance level of error (stated in percentage points)

$$n = \frac{Z^2 \cdot pq}{e^2}$$
$$= \frac{1.96^2 \cdot (0.7 \times 0.3)}{0.05^2}$$
$$= \frac{3.8416 \times 0.21}{0.0025}$$
$$= \frac{0.806736}{0.0025}$$
$$= 322.6$$
$$= 323$$

Therefore, the sample size of the study was 323.

3.4 Sampling Procedure

Convenient sampling technique was employed in the administration of the research instrument for this study. This was carried out by reaching out to the respondents based on their willingness to participate in the research as well as their accessibility and availability to the researcher. The total number of the research instrument (323) was divided by the total number of microfinance used in the study; this resulted in approximately 32 copies of questionnaire administered to each microfinance bank used in the study.

According to CBN (2020), there were 13 registered microfinance banks in Akwa Ibom State. The researcher conducted a pilot study to ascertain which MFBs implemented the service quality dimensions outlined in the study. The pilot study revealed that 10 MFBs indeed incorporated the specified service quality dimensions. Consequently, these dimensions were adopted and utilized in the present study. The 10 MFBs employed in this study were as follows:

1. Prudential Co-operative Microfinance Bank Limited – Ikpe Annang
2. Active Point Microfinance Bank Limited – 18A Nkemba Street, Uyo
3. Uniuuyo Microfinance Bank Limited, Uyo
4. Ini Microfinance Bank Limited, 4 Market Road, Ikpe Ikot Nkon, Ini L.G.A
5. Akcofed Microfinance Bank Limited, Ekit Itam beside water board, Itu, AKS
6. Madelyn Microfinance Bank Limited, 18-22 Ekpowong Street, off Marina Road, Eket, AKS
7. Nsehe MFB LTD 115 Ikot Ekpene Road, AKS.
8. Brooks MFB- 81, Nwaniba Street, Uyo, AKS

9. Cash Rite MFB, 28 Ndiya Street, Uyo

10. Stanford MFB, 142 Abak Rd, Uyo.

3.5 Methods of Data Collection

Data analysis involved both descriptive and inferential statistics. Data was analyzed using the simple regression analysis to determine the influence of responsiveness on customer patronage. All hypotheses were tested at $P > 0.05$ level of significance.

3.6 Sources of Data

The main source of data employed in this study was the primary data source. The primary data source was a structured questionnaire which was served on respondents. The questionnaire was made up of two sections: section “A” generated data on demography, while section “B” was made up of five sub- sections which were the independent variables (responsiveness) and the dependent variable (customer patronage). Hence, the ordinal scale used for this study were strongly agree, 4; agree,3;disagree,2;strongly disagree,1; neutral,0; to elicit responses from the respondents. The five points were employed to measure the dependent and the independent variables.

3.7 Psychometric Properties of the Instrument

a. Validity of the Instrument

The research instrument was subjected to validity test by the supervisor and other experts in the field of study. The relevance of each item in relation to the purpose of the study and the formulated hypothesis was assessed independently by the supervisor. Then the researcher used all the other observations made by the Supervisor and other experts in preparing the final copy of the questionnaire.

b. Reliability of the Instrument

The reliability of the research instrument was conducted to ascertain the degree to which the instrument yields consistent result. Hence, it was conducted to ascertain whether the variables of the study consistently measured the factors intended. In this study the internal consistency reliability was adopted, a pre-test for internal consistency measure using Cronbach’s Alpha was employed for assessing the reliability of the research instrument. The purpose of reliability test was to further ascertain whether the internal consistency of the scales is indicative of the homogeneity of the construct items that measures the variables. In the process, the reliability for each of these scales was determined at a minimum threshold of 0.7 and above (Cronbach,1951). Furthermore, the composite reliability (CR) for all constructs was above 0.70 (Serbetar and Sedlar,2016).

The obtained coefficients were:

S/No	NO.of items	Study Variables	Cronbach’s Alpha	Composite Reliability	1
4		Responsiveness	0.813	0.708	

Source Author’s computation (2023)

In this study, the Cronbach alpha for all the construct ranges from 0.813 to 0.708. All the constructs had Cronbach Alpha greater than 0.70 thresholds. Furthermore, the overall Cronbach Alpha coefficient for the instrument was 0.813, which suggest that the instrument used for the evaluation was reliable. (Cronbach’s Alpha > 0.70). In addition, composite reliability of reflective items was above the acceptable 0.7 threshold which means that all the variables in the study displayed construct reliability. All construct were viewed to have

acceptable reliability levels because the composite reliability scores for all construct were above the 0.7 threshold.

3.8 Instrument Administration

The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire with a 5 point Likert Scale ranging from 5 (Strongly agreed) to 1 (Strongly disagree). This consisted of Section A and Section B. Section A presented respondents personal data such as the age distribution of the respondents ranging from 18 to 50 years and above, gender distribution of the respondents divided into male and female, educational level segmented into SSCE, Diploma, HND/B.Sc, Masters and Ph.D, marital status of the respondents made up of single, married and divorced while section B presented questions on responsiveness, with 4 questions and customer patronage with 3 questions.

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

4.1: Data Analysis

Testing of Hypothesis

Hypothesis 1

Responsiveness does not significantly influence customer patronage of Microfinance Banks in Akwa Ibom State.

Table 4.3.1 Model Summary of the Influence of Responsiveness on Customer patronage of Microfinance Banks

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std.Error of the Estimate
1	.817 ^a	.667	.666	1.81574

a. Predictors (constant), Responsiveness

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Analysis of Variance of the Influence of Responsiveness on Customer Patronage of Microfinance Banks

Model	Sum of squares	Df	Mean square	F	Sig.
Regression	1934.599	1	1934.599	586.790	.000 ^b
1 Residual	965.998	293	3.297		
Total	2900.597	294			

a. **Dependent Variable:** Customer Patronage

b. **Predictors:** (Constant), Responsiveness

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Coefficients^a of the Influence of Responsiveness on Customer Patronage of Microfinance Banks

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	3.926	.265		14.836	.000
ResponseTotal	.476	.020	.817	24.224	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Customer Patronage

Predictors: (Constant), Responsiveness

Source: Field Survey, 2023

The regression result in table 4.3.1 revealed that the regression coefficient of R-value is (.817) which indicate that there is a strong positive relationship existing between Responsiveness and Customer Patronage in microfinance banks. The model summary table shows that the R-Square regression coefficient is (.667), which indicate that Responsiveness accounts for 66.7 percent of the total variation on the Customer Patronage of microfinance banks. The ANOVA table shows the F-ratio for the regression model which indicates the statistical significance of the overall regression model. The F-ratio value is 586.790 which is statistically significance at 0.000 level. Since the probability value (P-V=0.000) is less than 0.05 percent, we reject the null hypothesis and upheld the alternative. This means that there is a significant influence of Responsiveness on Customer Patronage of microfinance banks in Akwa Ibom State.

4.4 Discussion of Findings

The first hypothesis of this study states that responsiveness does not significantly influence customer patronage of microfinance banks in Akwa Ibom State. The statistical analysis of data in table 4.3.1 indicated significant effect of Responsiveness on customer patronage of Microfinance Banks. This is in consonance with Zebrga Zaveri (2020) which revealed that hotel customers become loyal when hotel employees respond to their request as well as when the employees become active to make customers feel secure in their transactions, when they give customers individual attention and understand customers.

SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATION

5.1 Summary

The main thrust of this study has been presented in the preceding four sections. This chapter is concerned with the summary of the study. The study investigated the influence of Responsiveness on Customer Patronage of Microfinance Banks in Akwa Ibom State. One hypothesis were formulated to guide this study and the hypothesis were tested at 0.05 level of significance through the use of simple regression analysis.

The five null hypothesis were rejected and the alternative hypothesis accepted. This resulted from the fact that the regression results was significant, the computed F-values for the hypothesis show statistical significance of the overall regression model, this means that there are statistical significant effects of responsiveness on customer patronage of Microfinance Banks in Akwa Ibom State.

To achieve the objective, a survey research design was used to reach out to the respondents of the Microfinance Banks in Akwa Ibom State. The population of the study was infinite. The Topman sample size determination formula at 5% level of tolerable error was used to determine the sample size of 323. The convenience sampling technique was employed in the administration of the research instrument for the study.

5.2 Conclusion

The study made the following conclusions.

- Responsiveness has significant influence on on Customer Patronage of Microfinance Banks in Akwa Ibom State.

This means that for every unit that responsiveness increases, Customer Patronage of Microfinance Banks will increase.

5.3 Recommendations

The first conclusion of this study revealed that responsiveness has significant influence on Customer Patronage of Microfinance Banks in Akwa Ibom State. Consequently, the study recommends that Microfinance banks employees should Show willingness to help their customers as well as providing prompt service to aid build customers trust, exceed their expectations and enhance their patronage. This is in consonance with the recommendations of Awaji-Ima and Carl (2022). They recommended that deposit money banks should be responsive in terms of their service delivery as it would enhance customer patronage.

REFERENCES

- Agodi, J. E., Aniekan E. A., and Oladipupo, A. (2016). Determinants of customers' patronage of fast food restaurants in Umuhia, Abia State, Nigeria; *Journal of Economic Research and Entrepreneurship Development*. ISSN 9876- 5432:vol. 2, No. 2.
- Oladipupo A., Agodi, J. E., and Aniekan E. A. (2016). Value Addition and Profitability Analysis; *Journal of Economic Research and Entrepreneurship Development* ISSN 9876-5432: Vol. 2, No. 2.
- Agodi, J. E., Ahaiwe, E. O., Aniekan E. A. (2017). Salesman's personality Trait and its Effects on sales performance: Study of Fast moving consumer goods (FMCG) in Abia State, Nigeria, *international Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development* Vol. 8, No. 24.
- Agodi, J.E., Kalu, A.O. and Awah, A.E. (2021). Impact of service recovery on customer loyalty of selected SMEs in Abia State, Nigeria, *journal of Business Administration and Management Science, Alex Ekwueme Federal University, 1(1), 143-150*
- Akpan, A. B. and Abdul, Z.(2009). Assessment of the impact of the of automated teller machine (ATM) on customer satisfaction the Nigerian banking industry, *Academy International journal of Nigeria*, International headquarters, Ahmadu Bello university, Zaria, Nigeria, 1(1), 64-76.

- Awah, A.E., Akpan, A.O. and Eno, N.A. (2021). Pull promotion in the marketing of bank services: among microfinance banks in Akwa Ibom State, *Advance Journal of Economics and Marketing Research*, 4(9), 1-15
- Awah, A.E, Akpan, A.O. and Sampson, E.A. (2021). Public relations and savings mobilizations drive of microfinance banks in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. *Advance Journal of Economic and Marketing Research*, 6(7), 11-16
- Awah, A.E., Akpan, A.O. and Ele, L.E. (2021). Personal selling and saving mobilization drive of Uniuyo Microfinance bank. *International Journal of Research in Finance and Marketing*, 11(10), 1-9
- Awah, A.E., Mfon, A. A and Ibok, N.I. (2024). Celebrity endorsement and consumer buying behavior of Generation Y: A case study of select betting business in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State. *Advance Journal of Economics*, 9(1), 1-14
- Udoh, I.S., Jospheh, U.E. and Awah, A. (2022). Service Experience and passengers' patronage of transit companies in the south-south region of Nigeria. *British Journal*.
- Etuk, A., Akpan, A.O. and Awah, A.E. (2022). Factors influencing the adoption of mobile apps among young people in Nigeria. A study of University of Uyo students, *European Journal of Business and Management*, 14(3), 65-73
- Etuk, A., Awah, A.E. and Akpan, A.O. (2022). E-marketing Strategies and savings mobilization drive of selected microfinance banks in Uyo Metropolis, Akwa Ibom State, *International Journal of Business, Marketing and Management*, 7(3), 1-6
- Udonde, U.E, Akpan, A.O. and Awah, A.E. (2022). Internal marketing and employee performance in insurance industry in Nigeria, *British, International Journal of Business and Marketing Research*, 5(1), 1-22.
- Etuk, S.G., Udo I.S. and Awah A. (2022), Customer relationship management and marketing technology, *Strat Mark communication consult*
- Etuk, A., Akpan, A. O., & Awah,A.E. (2023). Electronic banking and marketing performance of deposit money banks in uyo, Akwa Ibom State. *American Interdisciplinary Journal of Business and Economics (AIJBE)*, 10(3), 23-42. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8346738>
- Udonde, U.E., Awah, A.E. and Akpan, A.O. (2022). Effect of communication and empowerment on sales-force performance in the Nigerian insurance industry. *Advance Journal of Economic and Marketing Research*, 7(11).

- Etuk, A., Awah, A.E. and Akpan, A.O. (2024). Physical ambience and Customer behavior in selected microfinance banks in Uyo metropolis, Akwa Ibom State, *Top American Journal of marketing*, 9(1), 1-24.
- Bloemer, J., Ruyter, K. and Wetzels, M. (1998). Linking Perceived Service Quality and Service Loyalty: A Multi-Dimensional Perspective, *European Journal of Marketing*.
- Chattopadhyay, P. (2019). A Study on the Impact of Service Quality on Customer Satisfaction and Customer Loyalty with Reference to Service Marketing Context: Theoretical Approach, *Iconic Research and Engineering Journals*, 3(1): 89 – 96.
- Chen, S., & Huang, J. (2022). Measuring E-service Quality in Online Retailing: Development and Validation of a Scale. *International Journal of Information Management*, 64, 102289.
- Chen, Y. F., & Li, S. (2022). Examining the Role of E-service Quality in Customer Retention: A Study of E-commerce Platforms. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 63, 102722.
- Chen, Y. F., & Li, S. (2022). Examining the Role of E-service Quality in Customer Retention: A Study of E-commerce Platforms. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 63, 102722.
- Daramawan, D., Mardikaningsih, R., & Hadi, S. (2017). The Effect of Service Quality, Customer Satisfaction and Corporate Image on Customer Loyalty in the Banking Sector in Indonesia, *Journal of Business and Management*, 19(11), 46-51, DOI:10.9790/487x-1911064651
- Etuk, A., Awah, E.A. and Apkan O.A. (2020). E-Markting and savings mobilization drive of selected Microfinanace banks in UyO metrolopolis, Akwa Ibom state. *An international journal of Business Marketing and Management*.
- Fida, B. A., Ahmed, U., Al-Balushi, Y., & Singh, D. (2020). Impact of Service Quality on Customer Loyalty and Customer Satisfaction in Islamic Banks in the Sultanate of Oman, *SAGE Journals*, 1-10, DOI: 10.1177/12158244020919517
- Huang, H. H., & Hsieh, T. Y. (2022). The Influence of Service Quality on Customer Loyalty in Mobile Food Delivery Apps: A Study of Millennials. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 65, 102605.
- Iddrisu, A. M., Nooni, I. K., Fianlco, K. S., & Mensah, W. (2015). Assessing the Impact of Service Quality on Customer Loyalty. A Case Study of the Cellular Industry of Ghana, *British Journal of Marketing Studies*.

- Iddrisu, A., Norni, I., Fianko, K., & Mensah, W. (2015). Assessing the Impact of Service Quality in Customer Loyalty. A Case Study of the Cellular Industry of Ghana, *British Journal of Marketing Studies*, 3(6), 15 – 30.
- Ismail, A. and Yunan, Y. S. (2016). Service Quality as a Predictor of Customer Satisfaction and Customer Loyalty, *Scientific Journal of Logistics*, 12(4), 269 – 283, DOI: 10.1727011. LOG. 2016.4.7
- Ismail, A. and Yunam, Y. (2016). Service Quality as a Predicator of Customer Satisfaction and Customer Loyalty, *Scientific Journal of Logistics*, 12 (4), 269 – 283.
- Jiang, P., & Rosenbloom, B. (2005). The Impact of E-service Quality on Customer Loyalty: A Cross-national Comparison between the USA and China.
- Jiang, Y., Che, Y., Wang, S., & Wei, Y. (2022). Service Quality, Customer Satisfaction, and Repurchase Intention in E-ticketing: A Study of Online Event Ticketing. *Journal of Hospitality & Tourism Research*, 00472875211022613.
- Joudh, J. M. and Dandis, A. O. (2018). Service Quality, Customer Satisfaction and Loyalty in an Internet and Service Providers, *International Journal of Business and Management*, 13(8), 108 – 120.
- Khan, M. and Fasih, M. (2014). Impact of Service Quality on Customer Satisfaction and Customer Loyalty: Evidence from Banking Sector, *Pakistan Journal of Commerce and Social Sciences*, 8(2), 331 – 334.
- Kim, S., & Park, H. (2013). Service Quality, Trust, and Customer Loyalty in Social Commerce.
- Kuo, T., Tsai, G., Iuan-yuan, L., & Chang, J. (2017). Relationship among Service Quality, Customer Satisfaction and Customer Loyalty: A Study of Mobile Shopping APPs.